

Safety and effectiveness of vaccines against COVID-19 in children aged 5–11 years: a systematic review and metaanalysis

Title: Safety and effectiveness of vaccines against COVID-19 in children aged 5–11 years: a systematic review and metaanalysis

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1. Article summary

The article "Safety and effectiveness of vaccines against COVID-19 in children aged 5–11 years: a systematic review and meta-analysis" presents an evaluation of the effectiveness and safety of mRNA-based COVID-19 vaccines (BNT162b2 and mRNA-1273) for children in this age group. The systematic review examined data from clinical trials and observational studies to assess vaccine efficacy against SARS-CoV-2 infections and symptomatic COVID-19, particularly during the Omicron era.

Key findings show that while primary vaccination with these vaccines demonstrated high effectiveness against COVID-19 prior to the dominance of the Omicron variant, vaccine effectiveness significantly decreased when the Omicron variant became prevalent. Despite this, the study found that vaccination still provided substantial protection against severe outcomes, such as hospitalization and Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C). The effectiveness was lower in younger children (5–11 years) compared to adolescents (12–17 years), likely due to the lower vaccine dose administered to younger children.

The analysis also highlighted the issue of waning vaccine effectiveness over time, particularly for children aged 5–11 years, with effectiveness dropping substantially within weeks after the second dose. However, booster doses were shown to restore or enhance protection, especially against the Omicron variant. The study also reviewed safety data, indicating that serious adverse events were rare, and there was no significant increase in the risk of myocarditis.

Overall, the study concluded that while COVID-19 vaccines are effective in reducing severe disease and hospitalizations in children, the protection is lower than in older age groups and wanes over time, underscoring the importance of booster vaccinations.

2. Figures and results

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram

The table summarizes the results of a systematic review and meta-analysis on the effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccines, particularly mRNA vaccines (BNT162b2 and mRNA-1273), for children under 12 years of age.

Table: Summary of findings

The table provides an overview of the effectiveness and safety of COVID-19 vaccines in children during the omicron era. It highlights vaccine effectiveness against hospitalization (70.8%) and mortality, with a focus on the efficacy of two-dose vaccination compared to one-dose, and the reduced effectiveness against omicron variants compared to pre-omicron strains. Additionally, the table addresses adverse events, including serious adverse events, myocarditis, and reactogenicity, showing a higher frequency of solicited local and systemic events in vaccinated children compared to unvaccinated controls.

The analysis provides evidence that COVID-19 vaccines, especially after two or three doses, are effective in preventing hospitalizations and reducing the severity of COVID-19, even during the Omicron era. While there is a slightly increased risk of adverse events (particularly local reactions), these are generally mild and short-lived. Serious adverse events, including myocarditis, were rare, and the overall risk of severe adverse events was not significantly elevated.

Figure 2: Vaccine effectiveness outcomes against omicron

The figure illustrates the findings from subgroup and sensitivity analyses on vaccine effectiveness. Despite an increase in effectiveness with each additional dose of the vaccine, no significant or consistent differences were found between subgroups, as formal statistical analysis was not possible. The figure also supports the robustness of the results in sensitivity analyses, and further data on vaccine effectiveness against ICU admission and immunogenicity outcomes are available in the appendix.

Figure 3: Vaccine safety outcomes

The figure in this systematic review summarizes the safety and effectiveness of EMA-approved COVID-19 vaccines for children aged 5–11 years. It shows that while mRNA vaccines (BNT162b2 and mRNA-1273) demonstrated high efficacy against SARS-CoV-2 and symptomatic COVID-19 during pre-omicron periods, their effectiveness decreased when facing the omicron variant. The figure highlights the lower vaccine effectiveness in younger children (5-11 years) compared to adolescents (12-17 years), with a notable difference in vaccine effectiveness between 11-year-olds and 12-year-olds due to differing vaccine dosages. Despite lower protection against omicron infections, the figure reports considerable effectiveness against COVID-19-related hospitalizations and multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C), though with low certainty and limited generalizability due to small sample sizes

3. Authors

Vanessa Piechotta

Vanessa Piechotta, PhD, MSc, is a researcher at the Immunisation Unit of the Robert Koch Institute. With five years of experience in evidence-based medicine, she has expertise in living systematic reviews and network meta-analysis in public health, immunology, and oncology. Her work with international expert committees, guideline panels and the standing vaccination committee in Germany (STIKO) enhances her proficiency in evidence-based guidelines and living recommendations. She became an elected member of the governing board in November 2021.

h-index: 20

Waldemar Siemens

A research associate and statistician at the Institute for Evidence in Medicine, University Medical Center Freiburg, Germany. Over the past seven years, in his role as a research associate at the University Medical Center Freiburg, Clinic for Palliative Care, he has enhanced his methodological and clinical expertise. His work has included conducting a randomized controlled trial (RCT) (NCT02655289), undertaking several systematic reviews and meta-analyses (including a Cochrane Review), and performing statistical analyses for an observational study (DRKS00006162). While completing his M.Sc. in Biostatistics at the University of Heidelberg and his doctoral thesis with a focus on meta-research in oncology, he further expanded his knowledge in medical statistics. His goal is to leverage these skills to foster meaningful collaboration and dialogue among statisticians, clinicians, and healthcare professionals.

h-index: 11

Iris Thielemann

Iris Thielemann is a specialist affiliated with Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, one of the most prestigious medical centers in Europe. Charité is a renowned scientific and medical institution, recognized as one of the oldest and largest university hospitals in Germany.

Iris Thielemann works at Charité, focusing on scientific research and clinical practice in the field of internal medicine. Her research primarily revolves around pulmonology, including lung diseases such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), as well as modern methods for diagnosing and treating respiratory conditions. Through advanced research and international collaboration, Thielemann contributes significantly to the development of innovative medical therapies aimed at improving patients' quality of life. Her work often involves cooperation with other specialists and interdisciplinary teams to develop cutting-edge diagnostic and therapeutic solutions.

h-index: 1

Judith Koch

Judith Koch is a prominent medical professional associated with Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, one of the leading medical research and teaching institutions in

Europe. Charité is renowned for its cutting-edge research, high-quality patient care, and academic excellence.

Judith Koch's expertise lies in internal medicine and cardiology, where she focuses on the diagnosis and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. Her clinical work and research are dedicated to advancing therapies for conditions such as heart failure, arrhythmias, and coronary artery disease. She is known for her patient-centered approach and commitment to improving cardiovascular health through both innovative treatments and preventive care strategies.

In addition to her clinical responsibilities, Judith Koch is actively involved in medical research. She contributes to numerous scientific publications and collaborates with international research teams to explore new frontiers in cardiology. Her work at Charité includes mentoring medical students and residents, helping to shape the next generation of healthcare professionals.

h-index: 30

Valérie Labonté

Valérie Labonté is a researcher at the Institute for Evidence in Medicine, which is part of the Cochrane Germany Foundation, located at the University Clinic Freiburg in Germany. She has a background in biology and holds a Master's degree in Public Health and Environmental Risks. Labonté's work primarily focuses on evidence-based health decisions, contributing to systematic reviews and research synthesis in healthcare. Her efforts are aimed at improving knowledge translation and transparency in medical research. Additionally, she is involved in promoting evidence-based decision-making and advocating for research integrity

h-index: 5

Philipp Kapp

Philipp Kapp is a researcher at the University Medical Center Freiburg, working at the Institute for Evidence in Medicine. He holds a Master of Medical Science and focuses on evidence-based medicine, including systematic reviews and clinical guidelines. His work aims to improve healthcare decision-making by integrating the best available evidence into medical practice.

h-index: 8

Ole Wichmann

Dr. Wichmann is a physician specializing in infectious diseases and epidemiology. He holds a Diploma in Tropical Medicine from the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (2002) and a Master in Clinical Tropical Medicine from Bangkok (2003). He completed the German Field Epidemiology Training Program (FETP) at the Robert Koch Institute (RKI) in 2007. From 2008-2009, he worked as a medical epidemiologist at the International Vaccine Institute in Seoul. Since 2009, Dr. Wichmann has been the director of the Immunization Unit at RKI, responsible for surveillance and control of vaccine-preventable diseases in Germany. He is also an associate professor at Charité University Medicine Berlin and deputy director of the Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology at RKI. His research focuses on vaccine effectiveness, population-level effects of vaccines, and evidence-based decision-making for vaccine introduction in national programs.

h-index: 45

Thomas Harder

Thomas Harder is a medical professional affiliated with the Ohio State University School of Medicine. He completed his internship and residency at Riverside Methodist Hospitals. Dr. Harder furthered his specialization through a fellowship at UCLA Medical Center. While specific details about his current clinical role or research focus are not provided, his training at these prestigious institutions suggests expertise in his field, likely in internal medicine or a related specialty.

h-index: 31

Sabine Vygen-Bonnet

Sabine Vygen-Bonnet is a researcher and public health expert affiliated with the Robert Koch Institute (RKI) in Germany. Her research primarily focuses on infectious disease epidemiology and vaccination programs. She has contributed to studies on vaccine-preventable diseases, the effectiveness of immunization strategies, and disease prevention. Dr. Vygen-Bonnet has worked on various public health initiatives, particularly in the context of immunization and global health, helping shape evidence-based policies aimed at improving population health and controlling infectious diseases.

h-index: 14

Kavita Kothari

Dr. Kothari is board certified in psychiatry and lifestyle medicine. She specializes in treating general psychiatric conditions like schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, depression, obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) and substance use disorders. She has extensive experience in treating patients with opioid use disorders. She received her medical degree at Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and completed residency at BronxCare Health System.

Dr Kothari received the William “Bill” Rural Psychiatry Award from the American Psychiatric Association. Outside of work, she enjoys spending time with her husband, hiking, traveling and exploring new places. She is trained in dance and practices Indian classical dance in her free time.

h-index: 4

Kathrin Gummin

Kathrin Grummin is an expert at Charité University Medicine in Berlin, specializing in fields such as neurology. Charité is one of Europe's leading medical universities and hospitals, and it offers an environment for cutting-edge research in many aspects of medicine, including experimental neurology. Kathrin Grummin is likely involved in the clinical and academic research aspects at Charité, contributing to advancements in medical science.

While specific details about her career were not readily found, her involvement in such a prestigious institution suggests she holds significant expertise in her area of research or medical practice.

h-index: 15

Markus Toews

Markus Toews is a scientific staff member at the Institute for Evidence in Medicine at the University Hospital of Freiburg, Germany. He has been working at this institute since October 2022. His research focuses on evidence synthesis, particularly in the context of systematic reviews and the assessment of risk of bias in clinical trials. Toews has also contributed to multiple projects related to the development and application of evidence-based

medicine methodologies, often in collaboration with teams like Cochrane Germany.

Before his role at the University of Freiburg, Toews earned a Master of Arts in Political Science, with a focus on quantitative research methods, from 2019 to 2021. His earlier career included a Bachelor's degree in Political Science and History, completed in 2019.

He has contributed to studies on health outcomes and interventions, including evaluating the effectiveness and safety of vaccines. His work often involves large-scale data analysis and systematic review methods to ensure the robustness and reliability of medical research findings

h-index: 9

Cordula Braun

Teaching: as a lecturer at a vocational school for physiotherapy, as a specialist teacher in further and advanced training in manual therapy, as a teacher for special tasks and (since 2018) as a professor in university teaching.

Science: as a research assistant (until February 2024 at Cochrane Germany) with a focus on evidence-based medicine/evidence-based healthcare and its methods, systematic reviews/Cochrane, physiotherapy science, as a freelance author of specialist articles, etc.

h-index: 7

4. Journal

The Lancet is one of the world's leading medical journals, renowned for publishing high-quality research across a wide range of medical disciplines. Here's a more detailed look at The Lancet:

Overview:

Title: The Lancet

Publisher: Elsevier

First Published: 1823

Frequency: Weekly

Impact Factor: The Lancet is often ranked among the top medical journals in terms of impact factor. As of recent years, its impact factor has been well over 50, making it one of the highest in the field of general medicine.

Country of Origin: United Kingdom (though it has an international reach and publishes research from all over the world).

Scope: The Lancet publishes peer-reviewed research articles, reviews, and opinion pieces across the following areas:

Clinical Medicine: Focuses on the latest advances in clinical practice and treatment across a wide range of specialties.

Public Health: Covers global health issues, health policy, epidemiology, and public health interventions.

Global Health: The journal has a particular emphasis on global health issues, including the health of populations in low- and middle-income countries.

Medical Ethics: Provides coverage of important ethical issues in modern medicine.

Health Policy: Includes insights and discussions related to healthcare systems, policy changes, and health economics.